

THE ROLE OF POLYPHENOLS IN THE BIOENERGETIC SYSTEM OF RAT LIVER MITOCHONDRIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of specific polyphenolic compounds on the cyclosporin A (CsA)-sensitive mitochondrial permeability transition pore (mPTP) in rat liver mitochondria. Experimental results demonstrated that, under conditions where mitochondria utilized pyruvate and malate as oxidation substrates, the opening of the mPTP induced by 10 μ M Ca^{2+} was markedly suppressed by the polyphenolic compound hexahydroxydiphenoyl-1-(α - β -D-glucopyranoside)-2-(α -4-D-galloyl- β -D-glucopyranoside). At a concentration of 100 μ M, this compound reduced the conformational activation of the pore by $70.5 \pm 4.8\%$ compared to the control group, indicating a pronounced inhibitory effect on Ca^{2+} -dependent mitochondrial permeability transition..

Introduction. Mitochondria are key organelles involved in maintaining cellular homeostasis and regulating intracellular Ca^{2+} levels. Under oxidative stress, they are among the first to respond, leading to the activation of the cyclosporin A (CsA)-sensitive mitochondrial permeability transition pore (mPTP). Opening of the pore disrupts membrane integrity, promotes the release of pro-apoptotic factors, and triggers apoptotic and necrotic pathways. Oxidative stress also disturbs the cellular antioxidant-prooxidant balance and enhances lipid peroxidation, contributing to further cell damage. In this context, natural polyphenolic compounds are of particular interest due to their antioxidant, hepatoprotective, and membrane-stabilizing properties. Investigating their effects on mitochondrial functions is essential for understanding the cellular mechanisms of action and for the development of novel pharmacological agents of natural origin.

Materials and Methods. Rat liver mitochondria were isolated by differential centrifugation according to the method of Schneider [12]. The composition of the isolation medium was as follows: 250 mM sucrose, 10 mM Tris-HCl, and 1 mM EDTA, pH 7.4. The centrifugation process was carried out in two stages. At the first stage, centrifugation was performed at 1500 rpm for 7–8 minutes. At the second stage, centrifugation was conducted at 6000 rpm for 15 minutes. For the experiments, the mitochondrial suspension was diluted at a 10:1 ratio in the isolation medium without EDTA and stored on ice until use. The state of the Ca^{2+} -dependent permeability transition pore (mPTP) was assessed by measuring the rate of mitochondrial swelling. The optical density of the mitochondrial suspension was recorded at

540 nm at a temperature of 26 °C, with a protein concentration of 0.3–0.4 mg/mL in the incubation medium. The protein content was determined using the biuret method.

Results. In this study, the effects of hexahydroxydiphenoyl-1-(α - β -D-glucopyranoside)-2-(α -4-D-galloyl- β -D-glucopyranoside), a polyphenolic compound isolated from *Plantago major* L., on the Ca^{2+} -induced swelling of rat liver mitochondria were thoroughly investigated. At a concentration of 50 μM , the compound demonstrated a significant inhibitory effect on mitochondrial swelling triggered by 10 μM Ca^{2+} . Moreover, increasing the concentration to 100 μM and 150 μM resulted in more pronounced inhibition, reducing mitochondrial swelling by $65.2 \pm 3.5\%$ and $83.7 \pm 2.6\%$, respectively, compared to control. These findings suggest a dose-dependent protective role of this polyphenol against calcium-induced mitochondrial permeability transition, which is critical in the regulation of mitochondrial function and cell survival under stress conditions

Conclusion. The present study demonstrates that the polyphenolic compound hexahydroxydiphenoyl-1-(α - β -D-glucopyranoside)-2-(α -4-D-galloyl- β -D-glucopyranoside), isolated from *Plantago major* L., effectively inhibits Ca^{2+} -induced swelling of rat liver mitochondria in a dose-dependent manner. This inhibitory effect on the cyclosporin A-sensitive mitochondrial permeability transition pore (mPTP) suggests its potential protective role in preserving mitochondrial integrity under oxidative stress conditions. These findings highlight the therapeutic potential of specific polyphenols in modulating mitochondrial function and preventing cell damage associated with calcium overload and oxidative stress.

